

PROCESSING OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

C. Persad, Z. Eliezer, D. L. Bourell, and H. L. Marcus,
Center for Materials Science and Engineering,
University of Texas, Austin, TX 78712.

ABSTRACT

The use of powder constituents in the processing and fabrication of metal matrix composites provides diverse and flexible routes for the assembly of materials at the microscopic level. In the research that we describe here, the metal matrices were copper and tungsten. The dispersed phases were graphitic carbon, and boron carbide. Most of the processing was performed with the constituents in the solid state. In the high energy high rate processing, energetic high-current pulses are directly applied to a powder mass to provide pulsed Joule heating. Heating rates of 1000 K/s to 10,000 K/s are achieved. When heat and pressure are simultaneously applied, rapid densification can occur. A homopolar pulse generator with 1 MA current capability has been used as a high-current source. The investigation of binderless copper-graphite powder composites yielded materials with high densities, hardnesses and electrical conductivities. These materials have shown superior performance in terms of their high-temperature capability and wear resistance in high-current, high-speed, electrotribological evaluation. The tungsten-based composite system offers a metallurgical cornucopia of phases including W, W_2C , FeWB, W_2B , Fe_3C , Fe_6W_6C , Ni_4B_3 , and Fe_7W_6 . These are obtained by reactions in the multicomponent system: W, Ni, Fe, B, C. Some of these phases have large heats of formation and the consolidation proceeds by exothermic heating under pressure. The processing science based on these approaches has as a common focus the understanding of the influence of basic processing parameters - time, temperature, and pressure - on the microstructure and properties of these composites.

KEYWORDS: Powder composite processing, high-energy high-rate processing, Copper-graphite, Tungsten-Boron carbide, Evaluation/Testing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Of the many approaches developed for the processing of metal matrix composites (1), those based upon powder processing offer great flexibility in the selection and assembly of constituents. Conventional powder processing can be conveniently divided into primary operations such as mixing and blending, compacting and sintering; and secondary operations such as mechanical working and heat treatment aimed at developing near full density. Some of these primary and secondary operations are combined in new single-residence processes such as vacuum hot pressing, hot isostatic pressing, and quasi-isostatic processes such as rapid omnidirectional compaction and the Ceracon process (2). These offer a range of pressure-temperature-time combinations, which, when matched to particular materials systems, allow the investigation of a variety of materials responses.

Over the last few years a powder processing approach based upon the use of high-energy electrical current pulses has been studied (3). This high-energy high-rate (HEHR) process has been applied to several composite materials including copper-graphite (4-7), aluminum-silicon carbide (8), nickel-molybdenum boride (9-10), and tungsten-based systems (11-14).

In this paper we review the results on the copper-graphite and W-Ni-Fe + B₄C systems. These systems provide an interesting contrast in their processing responses. In the copper-graphite system, the constituents have virtually zero mutual solubility and a stable copper carbide does not exist. The graphite is thus metallurgically inert with respect to the copper matrix yet contributes to solid-state densification of the relatively soft copper matrix by accommodating strain and facilitating plastic flow. Easy shearing along the basal plane of the graphite particles enables this. In contrast, the W-Ni-Fe + B₄C is a highly reactive system with a reaction temperature threshold reported to be 1173K (15). This threshold may be even lower \approx 1000K based upon the W+C reaction (16). Beyond these temperatures, the metallic constituents in this system consume all the available carbon and boron producing a rich array of carbides and borides, and in the process releasing significant heats of reaction.

2. PROCESS AND MATERIALS DESCRIPTION

2.1. HEHR Processing. The high-current source is a 10 MJ disk-type pulse homopolar generator. The homopolar generator (HPG) is an electric machine that converts rotational kinetic energy into electric energy using the Faraday effect. It is a low-voltage, high-current (1 MA) device that applies high-energy pulses for a very short time. High-energy/high-rate (HEHR) consolidation of powders employing the homopolar generator as a power source has definite advantages over conventional powder metallurgy techniques. Since the energy is

delivered in a short time (about 1-3 seconds), this processing technique offers the opportunity to preserve the microstructure associated with the original powders in the consolidated material. Secondly, the energy deposition can be localized and concentrated at the interparticle contacts by manipulating film and contact resistances and the associated pulse Joule heating effect.

Figure 1. Schematic of the die arrangement employed in HEHR powder composite processing.

A schematic sketch of the experimental setup is given in Figure 1. The steel backing ring was used to prevent the spreading of the die liner, which often cracks during the application of pressure and subsequent discharge of the pulse. The material used for die liner was alumina. The electrodes were made from ETP copper or 304 stainless steel. Die inserts, in the form of foils or disks, were placed between the electrodes and the compact to facilitate compact ejection. Insert diameter was equal to that of the electrodes. The inserts were molybdenum, niobium, or stainless steel foils; or molybdenum disks.

Powder temperature and pressure are controlled by adjusting the specific energy input and the hydraulic pressure respectively. The specific energy input (SEI) is the amount of energy in kilojoules per kilogram of the powder mass placed between the electrodes. The SEI was calculated using oscillographically recorded current and voltage vs time traces. The power, at any instant, was calculated as the product of the current and the voltage. The total energy input was obtained as the integral over the total duration of the pulse.

2.2. Materials. The copper powders were dendritic (< 325 mesh) and were combined with flake graphite powders in mass ratio of 89 : 11. Detailed characterization of these materials has been reported previously by Wang, et. al., (5). The tungsten-nickel-iron + boron carbide were provided as a prealloyed and premixed blend. The metal:carbide mass ratio was 98.7 : 1.3. The metal matrix material had a W : Ni : Fe mass ratio of 93 : 5 : 2.

3. COPPER-GRAPHITE COMPOSITES

In the past, unidirectional graphite fibers/copper matrix composites have been extensively studied for use as electrical brushes. Although their behavior in the absence of current proved to be satisfactory, the passage of high currents increased the friction coefficient and the wear rate to unacceptable values; apparently, the lubricating properties of the graphite fibers are inferior to those of bulk graphite. One possible reason for that may be the desorption of water vapor from the graphite fibers at high interface temperatures (17). The substitution of the small-dimensioned fibers with powdered graphite to produce a copper + graphite powder composite was therefore pursued. Based upon promising microstructure/property combinations compared to commercial Cu-Cr-Sn-Pb composites, additional high-performance electrotribological systems are currently under development as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. Materials systems being investigated for high-performance electrotribological applications.

Contact Type/ Constituents	Development Status	Performance/Characteristics
Composite Brushes		
Cu-Gr-Sn-Pb	Commercial Material	Used in present generation of pulse homopolar machines. Fails at 220 m/s due to catastrophic wear.
Binderless Cu-Gr	Experimental Material	Proposed for use in future pulse homopolar machines. Hardness and conductivity exceed that of commercial material.
Composite Armatures		
W- Cu(90/10)	Experimental Material	Hardness and conductivity exceed that of the 90W-10Cu commercially available material.
W-WC-C-Cu	Experimental Material	Nanosized constituents increase population of potential contact spots.

Preliminary results of the tribological characterization of the binderless copper and graphite powder-based composites have been reported (4-7). The low speed pin on disk tests (0.6 m/s) of the copper and graphite on 4340 steel showed friction coefficients in the range 0.133 to 0.207 versus an average value of 0.120 for the commercial Cu-Gr-Sn-Pb composite. At high speeds the wear of the binderless composite is significantly lower than the commercial material. At 200 m/s values of $0.2-0.3 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3/\text{Mm}$ versus $2 \times 10^3 \text{ mm}^3/\text{Mm}$, are obtained over 6 km sliding distances.

Table 2. Properties of composite materials for brushes.

	Cu-Gr-Sn-Pb	Binderless Cu-Gr
Density (g/cm ³)	5.5	6.30-6.68
(percent theoretical)	82.2	94.1-99.8
Average Hardness* (Rockwell 15T)	45	62 (Axial), 50 (Radial)
Electrical Resistivity (μ ohm-cm at 300K)	37	3.82 (Axial), 8.95 (Radial)

* On this scale a fully dense copper powder compact has an average hardness of 70.7.

Everett (18) reported on the pulse duty (<3 seconds) performance of these binderless copper-graphite contact materials. An improvement in contact resistance was observed compared to commercial Cu-Cr-Sn-Pb composite material at velocities of 20m/s to 90m/s. Property comparisons of the commercial composite and the Binderless Cu-Gr given in Table 2, shows that latter material also has a lower bulk electrical resistivity. Current density comparisons at 100m/s and 160m/s showed the binderless material to have twice the current carrying ability of the commercial composite. When pulse loaded at 3kA/cm² at 160m/s, a nearly linear temperature rise of 100K/s was observed to a peak temperature of 420K.

The observed behavior depends strongly upon the intrinsic electrical conductivity of the composite material, and in particular of the copper matrix. One of the reasons for this is the limited exposure to elevated temperatures during processing. Figure 2, a plot of temperature vs time during consolidation of copper-graphite, shows that the time above 0.4 T_m (270°C) for the copper matrix is about 5 seconds. This short time is significant for plastic deformation under the 420MPa applied pressure, without deleterious oxidation.

Figure 2. Observed temperature vs time plot for consolidation of a copper-graphite powder composite to 95% density ($P_{\max} = 420\text{MPa}$).

One of the interesting features of these copper-graphite powder composites is their tailorable directional properties. Two orientations of the graphite particles depicted schematically in Figure 3 indicate the "edge-on" and "basal plane" orientations of the graphite in a copper matrix. Performance testing of these composites indicated that lower operating temperatures and reduced wear rates are obtained when "edge-on" orientation is employed. Figure 4 provides a snapshot of the high temperature capability and the cooler operating temperatures observed in the "edge-on" orientation. (These temperatures were obtained by a contactless thermal imaging method with $\pm 40^{\circ}\text{C}$ error band). We attribute this result qualitatively to the larger area available for metallic conduction through the copper in the "edge-on" orientation.

Figure 3. Schematic depictions of copper-graphite contact surfaces showing roughly disk-shaped graphite crystals oriented in "edge-on" and "basal-plane" configurations.

Figure 4. Plot of maximum observed temperature vs downforce for copper-graphite composite sliding electrical contacts tested in the two orientations indicated in Figure 3. Test conditions: $v = 200$ m/s; $j = 2$ kA/cm², $t = 30$ s.

Table 3 List of carbide formers (X) being examined and the methods by which they are introduced into copper-graphite composites.

X	METHOD
Ti	Mechanical Alloying of Cu-Ti compositions from elemental powders. Ti-coating of graphite powders using Ti-ethoxide precursors.
Cr	Mechanical Alloying of Cu-Cr compositions from elemental powders. Use of pre-alloyed Cu-Cr powders.
Mo	Mechanical Alloying of Cu-Mo compositions from elemental powders. Mo-coating of graphite using molybdic acid precursors.
W	Deriving Cu-W compositions from copper tungstates.

For many sliding electrical contact applications, wear in the binderless copper-graphite may be reduced further by chemically bonding the graphite to the copper matrix. However, because of the dominance of the electrical heating component on the temperature rise of the contact during operation (see Figure 5), both the thermal and electrical conductivity need to be maximized. The baseline Cu-C powder composite system provides a vehicle for the comparative study of a Cu-X-C interactions, where X is a carbide former. In the table above we list some of the approaches being employed to the introduction of X into the baseline binderless copper-graphite composite. Some of these such as Cu-TiC are also model systems for basic interface design studies (19).

The potential effectiveness of these additions on improving the performance characteristics of copper-based composite sliding electrical contacts depends upon a number of factors. Among these are their residual effect on bulk thermal and electrical conductivity, their influence on tribological behavior, and the bonding integrity of the carbide interfaces under thermal cycling.

Figure 5. Estimated contributions to the heating of an electrical contact carrying a 5kA current.

4. TUNGSTEN-BASED COMPOSITES

Pressures of 210MPa and 420MPa were applied to the powders and energy inputs were 3700kJ/kg to 4000kJ/kg. At the lower pressure, densities of 92% to 93% were obtained. The constituents remained in the solid state and the B₄C phase was retained. At the higher pressure, a density of 97% was obtained apparently through liquid-phase-assisted consolidation and the B₄C was fully reacted. Figure 6 compares the XRD patterns of the starting powders (a) and of the solid-state processed material (b) and that in which a liquid phase was formed (c).

The liquid-phase-assisted consolidation products are especially noteworthy. The EDS analysis of the metallic constituents in the matrix revealed a mixture of tungsten, nickel, and iron. The average composition of the matrix obtained from different locations in the matrix was 85.1 wt. % W, 10.3 wt. % Ni, and 4.6 wt. % Fe. Based on x-ray diffraction analysis, the phases identified were W, W₂C, FeWB, W₂B, Fe₃C, Fe₆W₆C, and Ni₄B₃. The intermetallic Fe₇W₆ was also observed. These reaction products were not observed in compacts consolidated at lower pressure, where the constituents seemed to have undergone solid-state consolidation.

At 420 MPa applied pressure, the boron carbide seemed to have reacted completely and the resulting complex borides and carbides were homogeneously dispersed. The matrix was homogeneous with the W : Ni : Fe ratio being approximately the same at different locations in the matrix. This process has the characteristics of "self-propagating high-temperature synthesis" or "SHS" (16). SHS is a reaction where an exotherm is involved thereby liberating thermal energy. This liberated heat helps sustain the reaction for a longer time without any external heat input. Material systems with SHS potential offer the possibility of using appropriately tailored electrical current pulses to bring a multitude of microscopic reaction zones to the threshold of self-propagation and then allowing the exothermic heating to activate full densification. This approach is currently being pursued in the Cu-W-C system.

Recently, studies of nanocomposites based upon W-W_xC have been undertaken. In the W-W_xC system, the synthesis/processing approach is centered around developing means for producing stable ultrafine-grained compositions. One of the composite powder synthesis routes being employed is the reduction and carburization of tungstic acid gels in flowing hydrogen and methane atmospheres. This effort extends the results previously obtained in microstructure control of ultrafine-grained tungsten powders from gel precursors (13).

Figure 6. X-Ray diffractographs comparing spectra obtained for (a) W-Ni-Fe + B₄C powders prior to processing, (b) Processed in the solid state under 210MPa pressure, (c) Processed with liquid phase assisted flow at 420MPa pressure.

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5. REFERENCES

1. T. W. Clyne, in F. L. Matthews, et. al., eds., Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials, Elsevier, London, 1987, pp 2275-2286.
2. Metals Handbook, Vol. 7, Powder Metallurgy, ASM, Metals Park, 1984, pp. 537-550.
3. H. L. Marcus, D. L. Bourell, Z. Eliezer, C. Persad, and W. Weldon, Journal of Metals, 39, (12), 6 (1987).
4. K. C. Owen, M. J. Wang, C. Persad and Z. Eliezer, Wear 120, 117 (1987).
5. M. J. Wang, C. Persad, Z. Eliezer, and W.F.Weldon, in J. Gully, ed., Proceedings of the 3rd.Int. Current Collector Conference, Austin, TX, Nov.1987, paper #20.
6. Z. Eliezer, M. J. Wang, C. Persad, and J. H. Gully, in , C. C. Sorrell and B. Ben-Nissan, eds., Ceramic Developments Materials Science Forum, Vol. 34-36, Trans Tech Publ., Switzerland, (1988) pp. 505-509.
7. C. Persad, et. al., in P. K. Rohatgi, P. J. Blau, C. S. Yust, eds., Tribology of Composite Materials, ASM International, Materials Park (1990), pp. 203-216.
8. H. L. Marcus, et.al., in F. L. Mathews, et. al., eds., Proceedings of the Sixth International Conference on Composite Materials, Elsevier, London, 1987, pp 2459-2467.
9. Y. W. Kim, D. L. Bourell, and C. Persad, Journal of Materials Science and Engineering, A123, 99 (1990).
10. Y. W. Kim, L. Rabenburg, D. L. Bourell, Journal of Materials Research, 3 (6), 1336 (1988).
11. C. Persad, et. al., "High-Energy High-Rate Processing of High-Temperature Metal-Matrix Composites," MRS Symposium Proceedings, 120, 23 (1988).
12. C. Persad, et. al., Proceedings of the Tenth Inter-American Conference on Materials Technology, IIE/OAS/SwRI, San Antonio, (1989), Vol. II, Section 30, pp. 33-39.
13. C. Persad, et. al., in A. H. Clauer and J. J. Barbadillo, eds., Solid State Powder Processing, TMS, Warrendale (1990), pp. 357-364.
14. S. Raghunathan, et. al., J. Materials Science and Engineering, A131, 243 (1991).
15. H. Sheinberg, in G. S. Upadhaya, ed., Sintered Metal-Ceramic Composites, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984, pp. 377-398.
16. Z. A. Munir, Ceramic Bulletin, 67 (2), 342 (1988).
17. Z. Eliezer, in K. Friedrich, ed., Friction and Wear of Polymer Composites, Elsevier, 1986.
18. J. Everett, MS Thesis, The University of Texas at Austin, Dec. 1988.
19. M. E. Fine et al, Scripta Metallurgica, 22 (6), 907 (1988).